

TAKRORIY GRUPPALASHLAR.

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Maqolada taqqoslamalar yechish usullari va shu usullar asosida birinchi darajali taqqoslama yechimlari, natijalar chiqarilishi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Takrorlanishlar, o'rin almashtirishlar, guruhlash.

ANNOTATION: Repetitions, substitutions, grouping.

Guruhlarni takrorlanishlar bilan ko'rib chiqamiz. Har bir $a_i \in M$ unga bog'liq bo'lgan qandaydir a_i sonini mos qo'yamiz. Bu α_i a_i elementning ixchamligi deb ataladi. Bu funktsiyani aniqlaydi. Qaysiki bunda argumentlar berilgan elementlarni funktsiyani qiymati esa natural sonlarni bo'ladi. Bu ko'rib chiqilayotgan mulohazani simvollar bilan belgilaymiz. Simvollar, elementlarni belgilashda ixtiyoriy tartibda yozish mumkin.

Masalan:

$$a_1 a_1 a_1 a_2 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_4, \quad a_1 a_2 a_1 a_2 a_1 a_3 a_4 a_4, \quad \dots$$

bu simvollar bir xil narsani anglatadi.

a_1 ning ixchamligi 3 ga, a_2 ning 2 ga, a_3 niki 1 ga, a_4 niki 2 ga tengdir.

Ta'rif: Agar har bir a_i elementiga moslashtirilgan α_i element ixchamligi N son bo'lsa, unda guruhlar takrorlanishlar bilan berilgan deyiladi. Elementlar ixchamligi guruhlar tartibining yig'indisini beradi. K -chi tartibli ixtiyoriy M dan olingan guruhlar takrorlanishlar bilan guruhlar takrorlari bilan n dan k elementgacha deb ataladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan simvollar elementdagi guruhlar hisoblanadi va shunday $8=3+2+1+2$

Teorema 3: Guruhlar n dan k elementgacha takrorlanishlari bilan quyidagi formula orqali ifodalanadi.

$$I_n^k = \frac{(n+k-1)!}{k!(n-1)!} = C_{n+k-1}^k \quad (10)$$

Teorema 3 ning isboti:

Ixtiyoriy guruhlar takrorlanishlari bilan qaysiki bunda a_1 element α marta, a_2 element β marta a_n element γ marta uchraydi. Endi bo'larni simvol ko'rinishda ifodalaymiz.

$$\underbrace{11 \dots 1}_\alpha 0 \underbrace{11 \dots 1}_\beta 0 \dots 0 \underbrace{11 \dots 1}_\gamma$$

Agar ixtiyoriy element bo'lgan guruhlar takrorlanishlari bilanda uchramasa qaysiki bunda uning ixchamligi 0 ga teng, unda keltirilgan gruppada birliklari yozilmaydi va shunda ko'rib o'tilayotgan simvolda nomi bilan 2 ta ketma-ketlik mavjud.

Simvollarda n dan k elementgacha bo'lgan guruhlar bilan 1 soni n marta uchraydi. 0 soni esa $n-1$ marta uchraydi. Bu simvollar 2 talik o'rin almashtirish takrorlanish bilan ekanligini bildiradi. Bu o'rin almashtirishlar 0 va 1 sonlaridan tuzilgan.

Shunday qilib, har qanday guruhdan takrorlanishlari bilan faqat bitta ikkilik o'rin joylashtirish mos tushadi. Aks holda ixtiyoriy ikkilik o'rin joylashtirishda qaysiki bunda 0 $n-1$ marta uchraydi. 1 esa k marta ixtiyoriy aniqlagan n elementdan k elementgacha guruhlar takrorlanishlari bilan mos tushadi.

Bu guruhning tuzilishi uchun har bir elementni 1 soni necha marta takrorlansa shuncha marta yoziladi.

$$a_1 a_1 a_1 a_2 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_4 a_4, \quad a_1 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_4$$

Quyidagi simvollar orqali ifodalanadi.

$$111011010111, \quad 101111111001,$$

Simvollar bilan

$$011100111111, \quad 110111010111$$

Quyidagi guruhlar mos tushadi.

$$a_2 a_2 a_2 a_4 a_4 a_4 a_4 a_4, \quad a_1 a_1 a_2 a_2 a_2 a_3 a_4 a_4 a_4$$

O'rnatilgan bu birxillik Γ_n^k songa tengdir. Shuning uchun (6) formulaga ko'ra

$$\Gamma_n^k = \frac{(n+k-1)!}{k!(n-1)!} = C_{n+k-1}^k$$

Bu bilan (10) isbotlandi.

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